

NEW METHOD OF SYNTHESIS OF ISOQUINOLINE DERIVATIVES.

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In continuation of the work of Ray and co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2510) it has been found now that the Me group of 1-methylnorhydrastinine is reactive to aldehydes and ketones other than nitro-aldehydes, under proper conditions.

Ray and co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2510) tried to prepare homologues of papavarine by condensing 1-methylnorhydrastinine (I) with different aldehydes, but the reaction failed in most cases, only *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde reacting satisfactorily.

This method, if fully established, would give an easy method of preparing isoquinolines. The conditions for the successful application of the method have now been found. In the present work an excellent yield of the important isoquinoline (I) was obtained by performing the Beckmann's transformation on the oxime of piperonylacetone, and this isoquinoline has now been successfully condensed with (i) piperonal, (ii) veratric aldehyde, (iii) anisaldehyde, (iv) propionic aldehyde, (v) acetone, (vi) acetaldehyde and (vii) cotarnine—showing that under proper conditions the Me group in (I) is reactive to aldehydes other than nitro-aldehydes (*cf.* Ray, *loc. cit.*).

In these condensations it has been found that one molecule of aliphatic aldehydes and the ketones condensed with two molecules of the isoquino-

line, but in the case of the aromatic aldehydes etc. the condensation takes place with one molecule.

It will be seen that a new general method has been worked out for lengthening the chain at position 1 or for introducing various substituents in this position. It may be mentioned that Child and Pyman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 37; 1929, 2010) found difficulty in synthesising di-isoquinolines analogous to emetine, but the present compounds of the type (II) have the principal skeleton of the emetine structure.

It is intended to study the amœbicidal properties of these compounds as soon as opportunity offers.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Piperonylacetone.—Piperonylideneacetone (2 g.) was reduced by hydrogen under slight pressure in ethyl acetate (150 c.c.) and absolute alcohol (30 c.c.) with 10 c.c. of 1 % palladium chloride. The reddish brown oil, obtained after distilling the solvent *in vacuo*; was crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 55°. The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 166°. (Found: N, 16.73. $C_{12}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires N, 16.80 per cent).

The reduced product was converted into oxime, which was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 100°, yield 3.5 g.

Preparation of the isoquinoline from the above Oxime.—To a solution of the oxime (2.2 g.) in dry toluene (20 c.c.), was added freshly distilled phosphorus oxychloride (8 c.c.) in small quantities at a time. The mixture was gently refluxed at 130-140° for 2 hours. After cooling it was decomposed with hydrochloric acid. The acid layer was rendered strongly alkaline with sodium hydroxide and the isoquinoline extracted with ether. From the ethereal layer, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the solvent was removed and the residue was crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 92°, yield 1.2 g.; picrate, m.p. 232° (*cf.* Decker, Kropp, Hoyer and Becker, *Annalen*, 1913, 395, 137). This method of preparing methyl-norhydrastinine gives better yield than the older method (*loc. cit.*).

Condensation of Methylnorhydrastinine with Piperonal.—To a solution of methylnorhydrastinine (0.4 g.), dissolved in alcohol (10 c.c.), well powdered piperonal (1 mol., 0.38 g.) and 4 drops of piperidine were added, and the mixture refluxed on a water-bath for 4 hours. After cooling

the product was poured into very dilute hydrochloric acid, boiled and filtered. The filtrate was first extracted with ether, and then basified, avoiding rise of temperature. A sticky precipitate was obtained, which was converted into its picrate in the usual manner in absolute alcohol, and was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 156°. (Found : C, 54·1 ; H, 3·2 ; N, 10·74. $C_{25}H_{18}O_{11}N_4$ requires C, 54·54 ; H, 3·27 ; N, 10·2 per cent).

Condensation of Methylnhydrastinine with Veratric Aldehyde.—The isoquinoline (0·6 g.) was condensed with veratric aldehyde (1 mol., 0·58 g.) in the manner described above. The condensation product was converted into picrate, which after crystallisation from alcohol, had m.p. 126° (decomp.). (Found : N, 10·35. $C_{26}H_{22}O_{11}N_4$ requires N, 9·9 per cent).

Condensation with Anisaldehyde.—A solution of the isoquinoline (1 g.) in absolute alcohol (20 c.c.) was boiled for 4 hours on the water-bath after the addition of 0·95 c.c. (1 mol.) of anisaldehyde and 7 drops of piperidine. The product was isolated as in the previous cases, and was converted into the picrate, which was several times triturated with absolute alcohol, and then crystallised from acetone, m.p. 192° (decomp.). (Found : N, 10·1. $C_{25}H_{20}O_{10}N_4$ requires N, 10·4 per cent).

Condensation with Propionic Aldehyde.—The isoquinoline (1 g.) and the aldehyde (2 c.c.) were condensed by the method described above. The picrate after crystallisation from acetone had m.p. 223°. (Found : C, 51·15 ; H, 3·97 ; N, 12·7. $C_{27}H_{22}O_{12}N_4$ requires C, 50·7 ; H, 3·6 ; N, 12·78 per cent).

Condensation with Acetone.—To a solution of isoquinoline (1·5 g.) in alcohol (25 c.c.), 5 c.c. of acetone and 2 g. of anhydrous zinc chloride were added and the mixture refluxed on a water-bath for 8 hours. The contents were filtered and alcohol was distilled off from the filtrate. The brownish semi-solid residue was suspended in water and made alkaline with sodium hydroxide solution and extracted with ether. The dark brown residue from the ethereal extract, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, was converted into picrate, which was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 180°. (Found : C, 50·6 ; H, 4·2 ; N, 12·34. $C_{21}H_{20}O_{11}N_4$ requires C, 50·68 ; H, 3·65 ; N, 12·7 per cent).

Condensation with Acetaldehyde.—To a solution of isoquinoline (1·5 g.) in alcohol (25 c.c.) freshly distilled acetaldehyde (10 c.c.) and piperidine (10 drops) were added and the mixture heated on a water-bath for 8 hours. The product was isolated in the usual manner, and then converted into the picrate, which on crystallisation from acetone had m.p. 172° (decomp.).

(Found : C, 49'97 ; H, 3'7 ; N, 12'49. $C_{36}H_{30}O_{28}N_8$ requires C, 50'10 ; H, 3'4 ; N, 12'90 per cent).

Condensation with Cotarnine.—Methylnorhydrastinine (1'5 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (30 c.c.) and cotarnine (1 mol., 1'9 g.) and piperidine (10 drops) were added to this solution. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 5-6 hours. After cooling, it was poured into dilute hydrochloric acid, and extracted with ethyl acetate. The acid layer was made strongly alkaline and again extracted with ethyl acetate. The extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and the solvent distilled off. The sticky residue, thus obtained, was converted into picrate, which after crystallisation from acetone had m.p. 237°. (Found : C, 50'05 ; H, 4'01 ; N, 13'37. $C_{35}H_{30}O_{10}N_8$ requires C, 49'7 ; H, 3'7 ; N, 12'97 per cent).

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